

Study on Stress among for Teachers in Mongolia

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to identify stress levels among school teachers and to compare stress levels based on demographic factors. There are 268 respondents sampled by teachers from individual schools in the Selangor area. A questionnaire was used, and a teacher's workplace stress inventory and teacher's workplace stress questionnaire was used as a tool. The study also found that high school teachers are more stressed in all stress factors that are associated with their parents, their colleagues, workloads, time constraints, student attitudes, recognition and support, and lack of resources than elementary school teachers. The result also showed that there was a significant difference in the average stress level for single and married teachers with an average difference (0.42, $p < 0.05$). It is hoped that the findings will help relevant authorities develop effective stress management programs for teachers to prevent the negative effects of stress.

KEYWORDS: Stress, Primary, Secondary, School, Teachers

INTRODUCTION

Stress is usually experienced by all men and women when they are not happy. Based on the organization's report, it was found that stress is becoming an increasingly threatening disease in the world. Researchers at the organization have found that stress is a global epidemic of the century (Seaward, 2006). This situation catalyzes the occurrence of the stress phenomenon, which requires special attention in order to understand. Currently, stress is ubiquitous and is often called a serious threat to the mental health of mankind (Andrews, 2005).

The teaching profession is a complex and stressful form of social service. Teachers and teachers must be sensitive to events. Thus, thanks to the implementation and a number of different reforms in the field of education, the role and responsibility of teachers would become more complex (Juraini, 2007). According to Jepson and Forrest (2006), a teaching career is a job in which stress levels are higher than others. Teachers' high-stress levels are frustrating, aggressive behavior, anxiety, job avoidance, absence from work and poor work (Rupp, 2005).

Teacher job stress is defined as discomfort, negative emotions such as anger, anxiety, pressure, and frustration stemming from their working aspects as a teacher (Kyriacou and Sutcliffe, 1978). In this regard, it is emphasized that one experiences uncontrolled emotions regarding changes in the educational culture, which requires the teacher to provide his knowledge, and at the same time, they must train

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students to be good members of the community. As a rule, a high level of stress leads to unsatisfactory work, absence from work and failure to work. Stress-adaptive teacher responses include psychological erections, physiological and alcohol and smoking-related attitudes, lifestyle, and insomnia. A poor working environment will lead to stress factors and lead to poor performance. Ultimately, the teacher will have a desire to quit his profession. Teachers' high-stress levels are frustrating, troubling, aggressive behavior, avoiding work, absence from work, and poor work (Rupp, 2005).

Realizing this motive, our country has high hopes for our school teachers. They are perceived as the architect, designer and guardian of the future of our children, who are responsible for their education. However, we must understand that teaching is not an easy job, like what other people think and perceive. In fact, teaching is a profession that always requires and changes (Johannessen, 2004). If you look at the Mongolian context, it seems that the phenomenon of stress among teachers is attracting attention. He also noted that stress levels among teachers are becoming more common and troubling due to the increased workload. In addition, a study conducted by the training center found that 70% of approximately 10,000 teachers across the country were depressed not only because of the workload, but also had to deal with the vagaries of principals, clerks, parents and students (Afzan, 2008).

Research goals

1. Determine the stress level of teachers in primary and secondary schools.
2. Compare the stress level among primary and secondary school teachers based on demographic factors.

METHODOLOGY

The study design is a descriptive quantitative survey designed to study a comparison of work stress between primary and secondary school teachers. Teachers from schools in the district that was selected using a simple random sample were included in the sample of this study. There are 11 secondary schools in 20 primary schools. The sample size was determined using a table by Cruchy and Morgan (1970). The population in this study is 512, and using the table of Cruchy and Morgan (1970), the minimum required sample is 220 respondents in two primary and two secondary schools.

Instrument making

Questionnaires were distributed to determine the respondent's initial information, stress level and stress factors. Part A requires respondents to fill out demographic data, such as gender, race, age, marital status, qualifications, and experience of respondents. In Part B, teacher stress based on the survey stress level from a study by Boyle, Falzon and Baglioni (1995) was adopted in this study. A pilot study was conducted as a guide to improving the items used. The resulting Cronbach alpha value was 0.957.

RESULT and DISCUSSION

This study was conducted on 268 respondents with 133 (49.6%) teachers from secondary schools and 135 (50.3%) from primary schools; 55 (20.5%) were men and 213 (79.5%) were women. Most of the respondents belong to the age group of 20-30 years (34.3%). The greatest number of academic qualifications achieved is 212 (79.1%) bachelors, followed by 47 (17.5%) and masters / Doctor of Sciences. Holders 9 (3.4%). Married teachers make up the largest number of respondents - 228 (85.1%), followed by single and unmarried teachers - only 40 (14.9%). Most respondents had 11-15 years of teaching experience, which is 73 (27.2%) of the respondents.

All seven factors tested showed that teachers in high school experienced more stress than teachers in elementary school. The results showed that there was a significant difference in the average stress level score for primary school teachers ($M = 2.13$, $SD = .558$) and secondary school teachers ($M = 2.54$, $SD = .834$; $T(9230) = -4.720$, $p = 0.0001$). These two methods indicate that secondary school teachers were more stressed than primary school teachers. Thus, teachers with high levels of stress cause frustration, aggressive behavior, anxiety, job avoidance, absenteeism, and poor work. Thus, this study can benefit all parties, especially teachers, the school and the

Ministry of Education, in order to improve the work of teachers.

CONCLUSION

Currently, there are many changes in the education system of Mongolia and of course, any changes will put pressure on teachers. Thus, teachers as catalysts for educational reform should be prepared to mentally and physically cope with emerging problems. Teachers should also be more able to cope with stress and always be ready to provide excellent services to create good students who will one day rule our country. This article proposes to further study the factors that motivate teachers to do good work, considering both internal and external factors. Thus, it is crucial to explore the most influential motivational factors that lead to excellent teacher performance. Further research should examine other types of external and internal factors of teacher motivation in various cultural and ethnic.

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